

Anti-diabetic effect of Bryophyllum Pinnatum leaves

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Abstract : Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder that affects the quality of life in terms of physical health, social and psychological well-being. In spite of the enormous progress in the treatment of diabetes using existing commercial drugs, such as, insulin and oral hypoglycemic agents, the quest and search for new drugs is imperative due to several limitations of the commercial drugs. In addition, the existing diabetic drugs are expensive and unaffordable by the rural populace in the developing countries. Therefore, the present study investigates and demonstrates the anti-diabetic property of aqueous extract of Bryophyllum pinnatum leaves. The anti-diabetic effect of the aqueous extract was demonstrated using diabetic rats (albino rats) as models, because of their similar blood components and physiology to human beings. At the same time, the anti-diabetic effect of the aqueous extract was compared to that of a sample containing a mixture of the extract and a commercial diabetic medicine, glibenclamide. The albino rats were made diabetic by injecting them with glucose D to raise their blood glucose level (BGL). Then a specified dose of aqueous extract of Bryophyllum pinnatum (BP) leaves was administered on the experimental diabetic rats, and their BGL was measured and recorded. The results showed a significant drop in the BGL of the diabetic rats to a value close to normal blood glucose level within 120 minutes when only aqueous extract from BP leaves was used. When a sample containing a mixture of the aqueous extract and glibenclamide was administered, a further drop in BGL was observed. Therefore, the results reveal that aqueous extract of Bryophyllum pinnatum leaves have significant anti-diabetic properties, and that the performance of the existing drugs (glibenclamide) could be enhanced with the use of the aqueous extract.

Keywords : Anti-diabetics, Bryophyllum pinnatum, Blood glucose level, albino rats

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